

JOINING OF PSZ CERAMIC AND NICKEL WITH ELECTRICAL CURRENT ENHANCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The joining of PSZ ceramic and pure nickel, by an electrical current enhancement method, was investigated. Fabrication was carried out at 1200 K, 6 MPa pressure and from 0 to 70 mA/cm² current. The shear strength of the joint reached an optimum at about 20 mA/cm² with an average value of 157.2 MPa when tested at 298 K. The strength for diffusion bonding alone was less than one fifth of this. The joint strength reduced to 79 MPa when the testing temperature was increased to 973 K. Observation by SEM revealed that an intermediate layer formed in the interface. This research confirmed that electrical current can enhance the joint strength.

KEY WORDS: Joining pair, Zirconia, Nickel, Current density, Joint strength, Shear strength, High temperature strength, Joint interface, Intermetallic compounds, Electrolytic cell,.

1. INTRODUCTION

Advanced ceramics offer great advantages over conventional materials because of their high hardness, excellent heat and corrosion resistances. In most designs, however, the ceramics are still required to be joined to metallic parts. A few processes are available for this joining including brazing and diffusion bonding methods which have been studied extensively. In the first case, active brazes, such as Ag-Cu-Ti alloy, are used but their low melting point and strength may lead to joint rupture in applications involving elevated temperatures or high stress concentrations. Although diffusion bonding can provide higher bonded strengths, the very high contact pressures and temperatures required are costly and may also cause harmful effects on the metallic parts during the joining process.

Zirconia (Zr₂O) is known as an oxygen ionic conductor. It is possible to join Zr₂O to metal by an electrical current enhancement method or so-called field assisted method^{[1] [2]}. In this technique, a joining couple, with an extra piece of metal as another electrode, is assembled as a symmetrical solid electrolytic cell, that is a metal/Zr₂O/metal sandwich using Zr₂O as an electrolyte. When an external potential is applied to the electrodes (metals), the charge is carried through the electrodes by electrons, but through the electrolyte by movement of oxygen ions. Redox reaction takes place at the interfaces between the electrode and electrolyte because

of the transfer of oxygen ions inside the electrolyte. Oxygen activity decreases at the cathode and increases at the anode which leads to the formation of a deoxidised layer at the cathode and an oxidised layer at the anode. The Zr_2O and metal may be joined by one of these electrochemical products. This is considered to be a solid-state process. Elevated temperature and mild pressure are required to obtain ionic conductivity of Zr_2O and very good contact at the interfaces. Hence, the procedure is defined as an electrical current enhancement method.

This paper describes joining of PSZ-ceramic and pure nickel by this method, and emphasises studies of the following aspects:

- the effect of electrical current density on joint shear strength,
- the elevated temperature shear strength, and
- the interfacial microstructure of the joint couple.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 JOINING MATERIALS

The ceramic sample was magnesia partial stabilised zirconia (PSZ, MS grade, from ICI Advanced Ceramic). It was sliced to discs of 20 mm diameter by 4 mm thickness, from larger stock, and their surfaces were lapped to a roughness of 0.4 Ra. Commercially pure nickel (Ni, 99.6% purity) was selected to join with the PSZ, because of their reasonable close match in elastic modulus and Poisson's ratios, as shown in Table 2-1. The Ni samples were machined to $10 \times 10 \times 10$ mm cubes and their joining surfaces were ground on silica paper (320 grade). All samples were cleaned in acetone (AR grade) prior to joining.

Table 2-1. Properties of the Materials to be Joined^{[3], [4]}

Materials	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion ($\times 10^{-6}/K$)	Thermal Conductivity (W/m K)	Electrical Resistivity ($\Omega\text{-m} \times 10^{-2}$)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
PSZ ceramic	205	0.31	10.2 (298-1073 K)	3.08	100 (1173 K)	450
Pure Nickel	207	0.31	13.1 (373 K)	79.3	43.89×10^{-6} (1173 K)	103(yield) 403

2.2 JOINING PROCESSING

Temperature and pressure were considered as important factors that affected the joint strength. The temperature selected was 1200 K because there is a eutectic point at 1234 K and 83.0 wt% of zirconium in the Zr-Ni phase diagram^[5]. A mild pressure of 6 MPa was applied to the sandwich, which is much less than the yield strength of pure Ni at 1200 K. The joining was carried out in a pressure furnace with argon atmosphere. The Ni/ Zr_2O /Ni sandwich was assembled vertically into the furnace chamber after the current leads were fixed to the pieces of Ni by electrical fusion welding. The upper interface between the Ni cube and PSZ disc was defined as interface I and the lower interface as interface II. The full assembly is shown in Fig 2-1. For most of the specimens, the external current went across the PSZ from the bottom to the top.

The first group of specimens was used to determine the effect of current density on the joint shear strength. The specimen was heated up to 1200 K under 6 MPa pressure and was kept constant at this temperature for 90 minutes. Within the first 30 min no current was induced in order to obtain very good contact at the interface. Subsequently, the current was applied across

Fig 2-1. Schematic diagram of specimen assembly

the specimens for 60 min. Six different current densities, from 5 to 70 mA/cm², were employed. After the joining the specimen was cooled in the furnace with a maximum cooling rate of 5 K/min. During the cooling process, a small current, about 10 μ A/cm², was continuously applied to the specimen to stabilise electrochemical products^[6]. In this group, the diffusion bonding specimens were just held at 1200 K, under 6 MPa pressure, for 90 min and no current was induced.

Another group of specimens was used to measure the joint shear strength at elevated temperature. These were fabricated with the same temperature and pressure as before, but the current density was fixed at 20 mA/cm².

2.3. TESTS OF JOINT STRENGTH

The shear strength test for joined couples was based on ASTM standard D451-91. The tests were performed using a Hounsfield Tensometer machine with a self-made fixture. The strengths at elevated temperature were undertaken with the same machine and fixture. A furnace, mounted on the machine, heated a specimen to the required temperature and held it for 15 min, before the force test was carried out.

2.4. SEM SPECIMEN PREPARATION

A few specimens were fabricated under the same condition as before, with different current densities (10, 40 and 70 mA/cm²). After joining, the specimens were sliced perpendicularly across the interface. They were polished with diamond paste (1 μ m size). Two kinds of solutions were used to etch the specimens for SEM observation. A solution of 50 wt% acetic acid + 50 wt% nitric acid was used to etch the nickel and 25 wt% hydrofluoric acid + 25 wt% nitric acid + alcohol was used to etch the interfaces.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1. EFFECT OF CURRENT DENSITY ON SHEAR STRENGTHS

The figure 3-1 shows the joint shear strengths vs current densities applied using the results from the first group of specimens. With the diffusion bonded specimens, it was found that both interfaces, I and II, between Ni and Zr_2O produced the same joint shear strengths with a mean value of 30.9 MPa. Whereas, when electrical current was induced through from bottom to top as shown in Fig 2-1, the joint strength at the anode (interface II) was reduced almost to zero (no joining obtained), and the strength at the cathode (interface I) was significantly increased. With the current density increased, the curve of shear strength rose up sharply within the current range up to 10 mA/cm² and then tended to an almost constant value, with a mean of 152 MPa. This was about 5 times that of specimens produced by diffusion bonding.

Fig 3-1 Shear strength vs current density at the temperature of 298 K

Fig 3-2. Shear strengths at elevated temperature (current density, 20mA/cm²)

3.2. SHEAR STRENGTHS AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURE

The shear strengths at elevated temperature are shown in Figure 3-2. With increasing temperature, shear strength reduced. The relationship between strength and temperature was nearly linear with a negative gradient. The mean values of shear strength were 98 MPa and 79 MPa at 773 K and 973 K respectively.

3.3. MICROSTRUCTURE OF THE INTERFACE

Figure 3-3 shows the fracture surface of the specimen (20 mA/cm^2 current treated), vertical view looking at Zr_2O side. The scratches, from lower right to upper left, indicate the direction of the shear movement. Transgranular cleavage faces, found at left region, show that fracture occurred on the Zr_2O side, and a few secondary cracks were extending into the Zr_2O in this region. At the other side of the photograph, many dimples and some secondary cracks appear on the flat surface. On the interim between cleavage and dimple zones appears a transition layer, which is a tortuous band (about $10 \mu\text{m}$ thick) vertically across the centre zone. This layer seems to be a product induced by the current.

Fig 3-3 Fractograph of the specimen (current density, 20 mA/cm^2), looking at the Zr_2O side.

Fig 3-4. Higher-magnification view of the dimple zone, corresponded to fig 3-3

A greatly magnified view of the dimple zone in the fracture surface, see in figure 3-4, shows many voids in this region. Some of these show traces of intergranular fracture and the others seem like transgranular fracture. No parabolic-shaped dimple or ductile stretched wall were discovered. This indicates that the dimple area was an exposed surface on the interface between

pure Ni and a transition layer or in that layer. The transition layer appears to have behaved in a brittle manner.

Those photographs reveal that the shear fracture occurred in the transition layer or nearby this layer, and it was a brittle fracture, branching along the interface.

Figure 3-5 shows the vertical profile of the joined specimen at the cathode (interface I) with 40 mA/cm² current during fabrication, viewed by SEM. The top side is the pure Ni, that presents two Ni grains identified by etched relief. The size of the Ni grains is far large than the thickness of the intermediate layer. The bottom side is Zr₂O₃, which has a very flat surface because it could not be etched. An intermediate layer, about 18 μm thick, was formed on the interface between Ni and Zr₂O₃ and its thickness is quite uniform along the interface. This intermediate

Fig 3-5. Vertical profile of the joined specimen (40 mA/cm² current density)

layer was observed in other zirconia systems^{[6] [7]}. The intermediate layer can also be divided approximately into three sub-layers from pure Ni side to Zr₂O₃ side. The first sub-layer, adjacent to pure Ni, could not be etched much and had a thickness of about 11 μm. Some pores and small rifts appeared between Ni and this sub-layer. The second was an etch-pit layer, which had a rougher surface. Then there was a very thin layer nearby the ceramic. The grain size in the last two sub-layers seems so fine that it could not be identified by SEM observation. This complete layer should correspond to the transition layer in Fig 3-3.

EDS analysis indicated that there was nearly 20 wt% of Zr in the first sub-layer. It means this layer included Ni-Zr compound (Ni₅Zr), which was the same in previous work^[6]. No evidence was obtained to explain why different sub-layers appeared to have different resistances to the etching solutions.

This intermediate layer also appeared in the other specimens with electrical current treatment; whereas, no such layer was found in the diffusion bonded specimens. This suggests the intermediate layer contributed to high shear strength. Many studies have suggested that high strength bonds were made when an intermediate NiO layer formed between the Ni and Zr₂O₃^{[8]. [9]}. This means that the high joint strength should have occurred on the anode (interface II) in our case. Hence, the mechanism of the electrical current enhancement method must be different from diffusion bonding. The main factor to control joint strength in this

method would be electrochemical reaction, although the diffusion process was still in existence because of the elevated temperature.

In order to understand the generation of this intermediate layer, figure 3-6 shows it from the cathode (interface I) in the specimen with 10 mA/cm² current treatment. The deep-etching zone at the top is the pure Ni, and at the bottom it is Zr₂O. The intermediate layer is about 11 μm thick and still consisted of three sub-layers, in which the second sub-layer is an etch-pit layer. There were a few characteristics distinguishing this intermediate layer from that in Fig 3-5. The first is the different thickness distribution of the sub-layers, the first is about 4 μm and the third is 3.5 μm. In the third sub-layer some dendrite formation and cavities were exhibited. Those dendrites were somewhat similar to the feature of epitaxial growing. EDS indicated the amount of zirconium in this sub-layer was far higher than that in the first sub-layer. The interfacial feature, appearing in Fig 3-6, could have been at an earlier stage in the electrochemical process than that from Fig 3-5 because of the difference of current quantity (0.01 Ah to 0.04 Ah),

Fig 3-6 Cross section of the specimen (10 mA/cm² current density)

4. CONCLUSIONS

(1). This work confirmed that an electrical current enhancement method was an efficient and economical method to join PSZ ceramic and nickel. Fabrication was performed at 1200 K and 6 MPa pressure in an Ar atmosphere furnace, with the current density up to 70 mA/cm². The current enhancement was at a maximum when about 20 mA/cm² current was applied and had a mean value of 157.2 MPa shear strength. At higher current densities, up to 70 mA/cm² the shear strength decreased slightly to be between 150.3 and 153.2 MPa.

For diffusion bonding alone the mean shear strength was 30.9 MPa which was less than the greatest achieved with current enhancement by a factor of more than 5.

(2). For the optimum current density the shear strength was adversely affected by temperature, reducing from 157.2 MPa at 298 K to 79.0 MPa at 973 K.

(3). The direction of electrical current applied is a critical factor for the joint strength because the maximum strengthening of the joint occurred only on the cathode of the electrolytic cell.

(4). A Ni-Zr intermetallic compound layer was formed on the interface (at the cathode side) when current was present. This layer consisted of different sub-layers and exhibited more brittle behaviour in fracture. Its morphology was dependent on the current quantity applied.

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N.B. The symbol Zr₂O for zirconia, has mistakenly been used in this manuscript, and should be replaced with ZrO₂.